

check. Each test entry was planted in two 2-m rows, spaced at 20- × 15-cm. Plants were inoculated at tillering stage with the ShB pathogen multiplied on rice stem pieces. Disease reactions were judged by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale.

Disease pressure was high (location severity index [LSI] = 7.22) for B1 and moderate (LSI = 4.60) for ShB.

CR280-5, JR49, and MGL 14 were highly resistant to ShB and 139 entries showed resistant or moderately resistant reactions. RNR788 11, WGL 26420, and

RGL 1746 were highly resistant to B1 and 39 entries had resistant to moderately resistant reactions. Although all the six lines with highly resistant reactions to one disease were susceptible to the other disease, 14 entries resistant to both diseases were identified (see table). □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Japonica cultivars are more susceptible to brown planthopper biotype 1 than Tongil hybrids

H. G. Goh, J. O. Lee, Y. H. Kim, and C. G. Kim, entomologists, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Office of Rural Development, Suweon, Korea

Susceptibility of Tongil lines (japonica/indica) with no genes for resistance to brown planthopper (BPH) was studied using a seedling bulk test. Four japonica and 4 Tongil lines that are recommended to farmers in Korea were alternately planted in 15-cm-long rows in plastic boxes with 2 replications. Cultivar reaction to BPH biotype 1 was recorded at 7, 9, 11, and 13 days after infestation (DI) using the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

Seedling reactions of selected rice cultivars to brown planthopper biotype 1.

Rice type	Variety	Damage rating ^a at given days after infestation			
		7d	9d	11 d	13 d
Tongil (japonica/ indica)	Milyang 23	R	R	MR	M
	Seogwangbyeon	R	R	MR	MS
	Pungsanbyeon	R	R	MR	MS
Japonica	Jinjubyon	MR	M	S	S
	Dongjinbyeon	M	MS	S	S
	Samnambyeon	M	MS	S	S
	Sangpungbyeon	M	MS	S	S
	Cheongcheongbyeon (R check)	R	R	R	R

^aBased on seedling bulk test: R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, M = moderate, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.

Japonica varieties Jinjubyon, Dongjinbyeon, Samnambyeon, and Sangpungbyeon were susceptible to BPH at 11 DI. Tongil lines Milyang 23, Seogwangbyeon, and Pungsanbyeon were moderately resis-

tant to BPH at 11 DI (see table). Among rice cultivars with no BPH resistance genes, japonica cultivars at seedling stage were much more susceptible to BPH than Tongil lines. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Rice tolerance for coastal salinity

T. S. Sinha, junior plant breeder, and A. K. Bandyopadhyay, senior scientist and officer in charge, Central Soil Salinity Research Institute (CSSRI), Canning, West Bengal, India

Rice varieties were screened in rainfed fields for coastal soil salinity tolerance during kharif (Jun-Nov) 1980, 1981, and 1982 at CSSRI. Trials were in a randomized block design with three replications. Soil pH was 7.0 and soil salinity (ECe) ranged from 6.3 to 11.5 in 1980, 6.3 to 8.3 in 1981, and 9.4 to 16.9 mmho/cm in

1982 at different crop growth stages. One-hundred and sixty-three varieties or lines were compared to local checks CSRI and Nonasail (Sel), using the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale. Plant survival at maturity also was recorded (see table).

In 1980 Nonasail (Sel) scored best at all stages. The lines IR4432-28-5 and IR2863-35-3-3 also were promising. In 1981 10 varieties or lines scored better than the resistant check at vegetative stage. Among them, IR9884-54-3 and M152 were the most tolerant. Although IR42 had 100% survival, it had poorer growth than IR36. Lines that performed

as well as the local check CSRI were IR4432-28-5, Nonasail (Sel), IR10198-66-2, and IR2307-247-2-2-3. IR4432-28-5, Nonasail (Sel), IR10198-66-2, and CSRI exhibited more tolerance at ripening stage than at vegetative stage. IR9852-19-2 and IR13426-19-2 had better tolerance at ripening stage.

Salinity was highest in 1982 and most varieties had high mortality and poor growth. However, M152, M242, PNL 28-23, and Nonasail (Sel) had 50% survival and performed best. Tests showed that there are three levels of salt tolerance: tolerance at all growth stages, tolerance at vegetative stage, and tol-